

Analysis of the Influences of Habitual Utilization of E-Learning Facilities on the Academic Performance of Business Education Students in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

The utilization of e-learning facilities on the academic performance has received more attention by Business Education students. This study examined the analysis of the influences of habitual utilization of e-learning facilities on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State. Two research questions were answered and two null hypotheses were analyzed. In this study, the population of 1,374 business education students in Delta State was used. The sample of the population consisted of 272 respondents, which is 20% of the population, using the systematic random sampling technique. Influence of E-learning facilities assessment Questionnaire (IEFAQ) was used as the instrument for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The major findings were that habitual utilization of smart phone influenced academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State; and that habitual utilization of e-library facilities influenced the academic performance of business education students in Delta State. E-learning induction or training is recommended for all categories of students' especially freshers in our institutions. The induction or training programme should be organized in form of a seminar from time to time, at the beginning of each session or semester. Students' should develop good/effective study habits by having a planned study programme at the beginning of each semester/session. This planned study programme should be strictly adhered to. This will make them to avert the ills in social media.

Keywords: E-learning, Habitual, Mobile Phones, E-library facilities, Business Education & Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

Tertiary institutions are beginning to embrace e-learning and realizing the potential power and implications for using it, as it relates to students' academic performance. E-learning involves the use of mobile technologies such as personal digital assistants and MP3/MP4 player and includes the use of web-based teaching materials and hypermedia in general, as rooms or web-sites, discussion boards, collaborative software, e-mail, blogs, wikis, text chart, computer aided assistant, educational animation, simulation, games, learning management software et cetera. In line with this fact, higher educational establishments in particular have dramatically transformed their mode of operation. Today, the use of chalk and duster in our seminar rooms and lecture theatres are completely extinct on some campuses. In place of that, we now have interactive whiteboards powered by computers and projectors, learning management systems etc. Electronic learning (E-learning) has emerged and progressed drastically with the development of the internet and information and communication technologies.

According to Fry (2000), E-learning is the delivery of training and education via networked interactivity and distribution technologies. Thus, e-learning simply refers to as learning and communication exercises across computers and networks or for that matter any other electronic sources. Khan (2005) pointed that E-learning has been described in various ways as learning using a number of different technologies and methods for delivery e.g. Computer Based Training (CBT), Internet-based training (IBT), Web-based instruction (WBI), advanced distributed learning (ADL), distributed learning (DL), distance learning, online learning (OL), mobile learning (or m-learning) or remote learning and learning management systems (LMS).

In E-learning system, students are able to interact anytime from wherever with different instructional material (text, sound, pictures, video and so on) through Internet. In addition, learners can communicate with teachers and classmates both individually and as a group discussion with the use of message boards, instant message exchanges and video conferencing (Al-Ammari and Hamad, 2008). E-learning system is an inventive approach for delivering, learner-centered, interactive, and facilitated learning environment to anyplace, anyone, anytime by utilizing the features and resources of different digital technologies along with other types of learning materials suited for an open, distributed, and flexible learning environment (Khan, 2005).

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Electronic learning is increasingly becoming the established practice with a wide array of positive outcomes. Over the past decade, e-learning, has moved from being a sheer project on the periphery to a central and integral part of some higher education operations. In fact, for some institutions it has become such an integral part of the institution that their institutional goals are reflected in their strategic plans and policies (Ellis, Jarkey, Mahony, Peat and Sheely, 2007). E-Learning means a lot of different things and it is understood differently by players with very different roles. The E-Content Report (2004) describes e-learning as “an umbrella term describing any type of learning that depends on or is enhanced by electronic communication using the latest Information and Communication Technologies (ICT).” Knowledge seekers no longer need to wait for information, training or instruction.

Undoubtedly, the survival of tertiary educational institutions in the 21st century will increasingly rely on various forms of electronic delivery system and communication facilities that are available in markets as requirements for educational flexibility. E-learning (EL) refers to the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to enhance and or support learning in tertiary education. However this encompasses an ample array of systems, from students using e-mail and accessing course materials online while following a course on campus to programmes delivered entirely online. E-learning can be of different types. A campus-based institution may be offering courses, but using E-learning tied to the Internet or other online network (Lorraine, 2007).

The variables of e-learning concentrated on in this study are: Smartphones and e-library facilities. E-library is a way of accessing materials for learning through electronic technology. Mobile phones are advanced computing capabilities such as a personal digital assistant (PDA), a media player, a digital camera, a GPS navigation unit, a touch screen computer, a web browser, Wi-Fi, etc. According to Gardner (2012) the uses of e-learning facilities of which smart phones are more prevalent have become a norm in today’s society vis-à-vis tertiary institutions. The uses are beyond the control and individuals frequently check their mobile phones with less of conscious. This is known as habitual behavior in many of scholar. Habitual utilization of e-learning facilities is usually identified as the signal of the situation driven automatically that occurs as a result of experiences. Stronger response of habits is one of the concrete structures that can overcome behavioral intentions. Habit is repeating response with the frequency characteristics without any of goals or

purposes that comes from thinking. Habit is active without consciousness with the minimum goals (Huang, 2014). Hence, habitual utilization of e-learning tends to have influence on students' academic performance.

Stephenson (2001) posits that there is little systematic research into the overall effectiveness of e-learning as a learning medium despite the great interest in it. Therefore, against the background of the foregoing, it became imperative for the researcher to investigate an analysis of the influence of habitual utilization of e-learning facilities on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State, with the view of analyzing the influence business education students habitual utilization of some e-learning facilities on their academic performance.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to analyze the influence of habitual utilization of e-learning facilities on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the influence of habitual utilization of:

1. Smart phone on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State
2. E-library facilities on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered in the study:

1. What are the influences of habitual utilization of smart phone on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State?
2. What are the influences of habitual utilization of e-library facilities on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the influences of habitual utilization of smart phones on the academic performance of business education students.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the influences of habitual utilization of e-library facilities on the academic performance of business education students.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Habitual Utilization of Smart Phone and Students' Academic Performance

Studies such as Jackson, Zhao, Kolenic, Fitzgerald, Harold, and Voneye (2014) and Ravichandran (2009) have proven that rampant use of social networking, texting and chatting on mobile phones result in lower grades and poor academic performance of students. While people of various ages find mobile phones convenient and useful, younger generations tend to appreciate them more and be more dependent on them. The researches have proven that some students have the habit of keeping their mobile phones on during classes and studies, even in the library, thereby distracting others.

Smart mobile phone is also helpful to the students for exchanging useful information with their classmates about their studies. Students use this fascinating magic device also in a very better way. Some of the studies proved that this technology has increased the academic performance. In this context the study tried to find out the positive effects on learning achievements of youth (Sundari, 2015).

The use of cell phones is on the increase with the global cellular phone market standing at 1.8 billion subscribers in 2007 and was estimated to increase to 3 billion by the year 2010 (Reid and Reid, 2007). It is estimated that 95 per cent of young people use web based enabled mobile phones

in Japanese societies with voice calling being the commonly used and brings about 80 per cent revenue. This growth is not limited to Japan, but has been observed in African countries such as Namibia. Significant growth has also been observed in the use of Short Message Services (SMS), a trend observed among young cell phone users. The increasing use of SMS is predicted to dominate both traffic volume and is likely to boost revenue generation for cell phone operators.

As Ling (2004) puts it, the line between a computer and a smart phone is increasingly becoming blurred as smart phones now function as computers and are increasingly being used for academic purposes. Cell phones as communication devices serve a very potent and imperative role in the academic settings. Hendrikz et al (2009) carried out a study on the effects of SMS on distance student's performance at the University of Pretoria, South Africa. The findings of this survey show that distance students who had academic rapport with their lecturers via SMS performed much better than those that did not use this platform. The finding of this study is significant in that it shows that cell phone use can aid the learning processes by simplifying the communication between students and their lecturers.

Ravichandran (2009) study shows that a mobile phone is a total blessing to human life as it provides a collection of communication media which add value to the quality of human life. A mobile phone is a combination of a clock for time management, a calendar to manage daily activities, a camera to take pictures and build memories, music player for entertainment, a radio to keep one informed of the latest happenings and is an Internet device to surf and download items and therefore, it is perceived as a mobile library.

Nonetheless, cell phones use can also be addictive according to Jones (2014). It can negatively impact on personal interactive skills of users, create emotional distance and discourage physical learning process. Although mobile phones provide a convenient form of information sources, they, however, lead to lackadaisical tendency as students don't see the need of patronizing the libraries as information is readily available on their mobile phones.

Mobile phone has been popular since the late 1990s (Meek, 2006) and today, with seven (7) billion mobile connections worldwide and unique mobile subscriptions of over 3.5 billion (Twum, 2011), they are very popular with young people and are commonplace in our educational institutions.

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These phones are no more just voice communication tools. Functions like Short Message Service (SMS) or texting have become global phenomenon. Not many of us keep wallet photos of loved ones. Now we save photos in our mobile phones, and view them on a touch of the screen.

Research on the influence of mobile phone on our schools today has not been given much attention. There is the conflicting priority of young people, parents and teachers in relation to the mobile phone device, with teachers more concerned about issues such as discipline in the classroom and parents worried about means of contacting their children at every point in time. Researchers have discovered that the use of mobile phone in schools is problematic. As Ling and Helmersen (2000) states, the mobile phone is “at cross purpose with the mission of the school”. While in school students are supposed to take on their prescribed roles as students with full concentration on their studies and free from contact with the outside world. However, the mobile phone gives room to blending students’ roles with other roles thus distracting and disrupting the students’ academic work (Gergen, 2002; and Halpen, 2003;). In the past when fixed telephones were the norm in schools, there were minimum distractions and disruptions but presently with the invasion of mobile phone and the eagerness of parents to maintain contact with their wards, the device is becoming part of the classroom. Thus, the mobile phone has the power to undermine the schools’ authority and weaken their control over students as well as influences their level of academic performances.

Jackson, et al (2014) opined that mobile phones' usage is negatively impacting students' academic performance. This means that the students who spent more time using mobile phone are having low GPA. On how much time they spend using their mobile phones and in how many classes they use mobile phone, they found that there is negative relationship between these two questions with students GPA. That is the students who are using mobile phone almost 7-10 hours and those who use mobile phone during most of their classes are having low GPA. He also found that one of the most useful features of mobile phone is text messaging used by 67% students (female 37% and male 30%). Almost 81% of the students (female 46%, male 35%) used standard text messages as compared to multimedia messages or other. Forty-three percent (43%) of students (31% female and 13% male) say that they put their mobile phone on silent mode while attending classes. Thirty-five percent (35%) of students (20% female and 15% male) say that they occasionally receive or send text messages while the class was in session. Fifty-five percent (55%) of students (35% female and

20% male) agree on policy that mobile phone should be kept by students but they should set it in vibration mode. Sixty-one percent (61%) of students (40% female, 21% male) say that they do not use night packages on their mobile phone. Forty-two percent (42%) of students (23% female, 19% male) say that they use day packages on their mobile phone. Sixty-seven percent (67%) of students (39% female, 27% male) say that they spent 10% of their pocket money on mobile phones. Fifty-six percent (56%) of students (32% female, 24% male) say that they sometimes use their mobile phone while doing their assignments.

Mobile phones are very common communication devices among University students. Almost every student of a university possesses one or more mobile phones. It is common phenomena among the teenagers (Cambell, 2006). It is affecting their social behaviour, health and budget (Ravichandran, 2009). However Ishii (2011) rejected the hypothesis of adverse effects of mobile phones on adolescents in Japan. But Jamal, Robbins and Tessler (2012) agree with the adverse effects of mobile phones on female students of Saudi Arabia. The use of mobile phones is increasing cost of education in the sense that in china about 22% of the University students change their mobile sets annually and 78% replace it after every two to three years (Khan, Khan and Amin, 2014).

Habitual Utilization of E-library Facilities and Students' Academic Performance

Studies such as George (2011) and Lonsdale (2003) have shown that there is a strong connection between the students' use of school e-library and their academic performance. Students that use the school e-library often perform better in test and examination than students who fail to use the school library. That school e-libraries have positive impact on students' achievement. It contended that more than sixty (60) studies have been conducted in nineteen (19) U.S. States and one Canadian province. It maintained that the major finding of these studies is that students with access to well-supported school library media programme with a qualified school library media specialist scored higher on reading assessments regardless of their socio-economic statuses. Also, it observed that a study conducted in Ohio revealed that 99.4% of students surveyed believed that their school librarians and school media programmes helped them succeed in school. It cited Lonsdale (2003) who reported a similar conclusion in Australia.

Earlier, Dent (2006) conducted a research on the observations of school library impact at two rural Ugandan schools and submitted that the purpose of the study was to explore connections between the presence of a library and certain students' academic engagement indicators, such as scholastic performance, reading and library use patterns.

According to International Federation of Library Association (2009) the followings are essential to the development of literacy, information literacy, learning and culture; and are core school library services:

1. Supporting and enhancing educational goals as outlined in the school mission and curriculum.
2. Developing and sustaining in children the habit and enjoyment of reading and learning, and the use of libraries throughout their lives.
3. Offering opportunity for experiences in creating and using information for knowledge, understanding, imagination and enjoyment.
4. Supporting all students in learning and practicing skills for evaluating and using information, regardless of form, format or medium, including sensitivity to the mode of communication within the community.
5. Providing access to local, regional, national and global resources and opportunities that expose learners to diverse ideas, experiences and opinions.
6. Organizing activities that encourage cultural and social awareness and sensitivity.
7. Working with students, teachers, administrators and parents to achieve the mission of the school.
8. Proclaiming the concept that intellectual freedom and access to information are essential to effective and responsible citizenship and participation in a democracy
9. Promoting reading and resources and services of the school library to the whole school community and beyond.

School e-library is very important in shaping students' habit as regards reading for leisure, to pass examinations and to obtain information on different aspects of life (George, 2011). It is an inexhaustible store house of unrestricted information resources in diverse formats systematically

organized for users. Thus, a school library cannot be separated from the school – parent institution and expect all round development of the students. Library users make use of library for different purposes. While some users use it for reading their notes and personal books, others use library to do assignments. Yet, others visit library to prepare for examination, recreation and relaxation.

Ogunbote and Odunewu (2008) cited Kumar (1991) and stated that the performance of students could be improved considerably if they use the library regularly. Students should therefore maximize the use of school e-libraries to their advantage since school libraries provide environment where the students can discover and develop their abilities and talents as well as improving their reading and study skills.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. This design is considered most appropriate for the study because a survey design, utilizes questionnaire, observations, tests, and interviews as tools in obtaining information. The population was 1,374 business education students in the four State owned tertiary institutions in Delta State. The population is made up of business education students from Delta State University Abraka (384), University of Delta, Agbor (297), College of Education, Mosogar (DELSU affiliate and regular NCE), (342), and College of Education Warri (DELSU affiliate and regular NCE) (351) in the 2024/2025 academic session. The sample for the study consisted of 272 respondents, which is 20% of the population. The systematic random sampling technique was used in arriving at the sample size. Influences of E-learning Facilities Assessment Questionnaire (IEFAQ) developed by the researcher, was used as the instrument for data collection. The validity of the research instrument was determined by three experts. Cronbach Alpha approach was used to determine the reliability, smart Phones cluster yielded 0.81 coefficient while e-library facility cluster yielded 0.91 coefficient. Mean and standard deviation were employed in answering the research questions, while t-test statistic was employed in testing the null hypotheses formulated at 0.05 levels of significance.

RESULTS

Results were presented in tables according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1

What are the influences of habitual utilization of smart phone on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State?

The data collected to answer the research question is presented in Table I.

Table 1: Influences of Habitual Utilization of Mobile Phone

S/N	Items	N	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Texting/chatting on mobile phone influence academic performance	272	2.66	0.69	Agree
2.	Keep mobile phone on during distracts students	272	2.83	0.93	Agree
3.	Diverts money meant for academics to buying recharge cards	272	2.68	0.96	Agree
4.	Distractions through my mobile phone during personal studies	272	2.91	0.86	Agree
5.	Mobile phones enhances the making of friends among students than real academic exercise	272	2.79	0.95	Agree
	Grand Mean		2.53		Agree

The result of the data analysis presented in Table 1 revealed that habitual utilization of mobile phone influences academic performance of business education students in Delta State. This is because, all the items in the above table obtained mean value above 2.50 and a grand mean of 2.53. The standard deviation values which ranged from .69 to .96 showed that the opinions of the respondents were not too far from the mean.

Research Question 2

What are the influences of habitual utilization of e-library facilities on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State?

The data collected to answer the research question is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Influence of Habitual Utilization of E-Library Facilities

S/N	ITEMS	N	\bar{x}	SD	decision
6.	e-library usage influences students' academic performance	272	2.77	0.92	Agree
7.	Lack of requisite e-library infrastructure influences my academic performance	272	2.76	0.84	Agree
8.	Non-cultivation of habitual use of the e-library influences my academic performance	272	2.79	0.77	Agree
9.	My institutional policies on the utilization of e-library influences my academic performances	272	2.75	0.77	Agree
10.	Lack of required competencies in using e-library influences my academic performance adversely	272	3.11	0.69	Agree
Grand Mean			2.83		Agree

The result of data analysis presented in Table 2 revealed that habitual utilization of e-library facilities influences the academic performance of business education students in Delta State. This is because the grand mean of 2.83 obtained is greater than 2.50. The standard deviation values which ranged from .69 to .92 showed that the opinions of the respondents were not too far from the mean.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the influences of habitual utilization of smart phones on the academic performance of business education students.

Table 3: Responses of Male and Female on the Influences of habitual utilization of Smart Phones on the Academic Performance of Business Education Students in Delta State

S/N	Gender	N	\bar{x}	S.D	D.F	t-Cal	t- Critical	Decision
1.	Male	146	3.21	0.76	270	7.94	0.030	Reject
	Female	126	2.39	0.93				
2.	Male	146	3.08	0.80	270	8.29	0.031	Reject
	Female	126	2.22	0.91				
3.	Male	146	3.27	0.65	270	8.15	0.000	Reject
	Female	126	2.50	0.90				
4.	Male	146	3.19	0.80	270	8.40	0.058	Reject
	Female	126	2.32	0.91				
5.	Male	146	3.18	0.82	270	8.93	0.723	Reject
	Female	126	2.30	0.80				
Grand Mean						8.34		

The result of the t-test analysis presented in the Table 3 reveals that there were significant differences in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the influences of habitual utilization of smart phones on the academic performances of business education students in Delta State. This is because the t-calculated values obtained in all the items as shown on the table are greater than the t-critical values. Based on this, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students

on the influence of habitual utilization of smart phones on the academic performances of business education students in Delta State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Delta North and Delta Central Senatorial Districts respondents on the influences of habitual utilization of e-library facilities on the academic performance of business education students.

Table 4: Responses of Delta North and Delta Central Senatorial Districts Respondents on the Influences of habitual utilization of E-library Facilities on the Academic Performance of Business Education Students.

S/N	Zones	N	\bar{x}	S.D	D.F	T-Calculated	T- Critical	Decision
6.	Delta North	146	3.04	0.74	270	6.50	0.001	Reject
	Delta Central	126	2.42	0.82				
7.	Delta North	146	3.05	0.63	270	6.54	0.000	Reject
	Delta Central	126	2.48	0.80				
8.	Delta North	146	2.95	0.67	270	4.84	0.000	Reject
	Delta Central	126	2.51	0.80				
9.	Delta North	146	3.05	0.70	270	1.612	0.394	Reject
	Delta Central	126	3.10	0.67				
10.	Delta North	146	3.08	0.73	270	1.772	0.212	Reject
	Delta Central	126	3.23	0.62				
Grand Mean						4.252	0.1214	Reject

The result of the t-test analysis presented in Table 4 reveals that there is significant difference in the mean response of Delta north and Delta Central Senatorial Districts respondents on the influences of habitual utilization of e-library facilities on the academic performance of business education students in colleges of education in Delta State; this is because the t-calculated values obtained in all the items as shown on the table are greater than the t-critical value obtained in all the items.

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Based on this, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that there is significant difference in their responses.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Influence of Habitual Utilization of Smart Phones on Students Academic Performance

The result of the data analysis presented in Table I revealed that habitual utilization of smart phone influences academic performance of business education students in Delta State.. The finding of this study is in line with that of Kibona and Mgaya (2015) who carried out a study on smart phone' effects on academic performance of higher degree students: A case study of Ruaha Catholic University –Iringa, Tanzania. It was discovered that the use of smart phone was abuse to the point of addiction. It was becoming more problematic in Tanzania because most students whether higher degree students or low level students were more addicted to applications found on smart phones such as whatsapp, twitter, facebook and the like. The study aimed at finding out the impact of smart phones were surveyed regarding the use of smart phone to their academic performance. Data collected after survey were analyzed using SPSS and excel tools, and then. Percentage analysis was done to find the key contributors towards academic performance and smart phone usage or addiction.

Kibona and Mgaya's study is related to this present-study in that both studies were on the "influence of mobile (smart phone) on the academic performance of students. The findings of both study equally relates in that both studies focuses on students of higher institution of learning. The gap between the present study and the later was that they were not conducted in the same area. The sample and population of both studies are not the same.

Influence of Habitual Utilization of e-library Facilities on Business Education Students Academic Performance

The result of data analysis presented in table 2 revealed that habitual utilization of e-library facilities influence academic performance of business education students in Delta State. The finding of this study is in line with that of Ikyumen and Fiase (2016) who carried out a study on e-learning resources availability and level of preparedness for utilization of educators in tertiary teacher

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educational institution in Nigeria. Ikyumen and Fiase's (2016) discovered that even though some institutions possess e-resources, their educators are not adequately prepared in terms of skills and proficiency for their utilization. Ikyumen and Fiase's study is related in that both studies focus on the utilization of the availability of e-library facilities for effective academic performances in the tertiary institutions. The studies also related in that both studies use questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. Both studies further related in that both research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while hypotheses were also tested using t-test statistical tools

CONCLUSION

The study was carried out in Delta State and focused on the analysis of the influences of habitual utilization of e-learning facilities on the academic performance of business education students in Delta State. It is however concluded that habitual utilization of smart phones, and e-library facilities influences academic performance of business education students in Delta State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made to stir students up towards a better academic performance:

1. E-learning induction or training is recommended for all categories of students' especially fresher's in our institutions. The induction or training programme should be organized in form of a seminar from time to time, at the beginning of each session or semester.
2. Students' should develop good /effective study habits by having a planned study programme at the beginning of each semester / session. This planned study programme should be strictly adhered to. This will make them to advert the ills in social media
3. Students' should learn to study their academic materials over and over again, as familiarity facilitates learning. This can be easily achieved when they are engaged in both personal and group study.
4. The positive side of social media should be harnessed by students towards a better academic performance.

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